

GRACE SITE INCLUSION FRAMEWORK

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SITE SELECTION STRATEGY

To ensure **global representation** in the **GRACE** study, sites will be selected to ensure:

- Representation of **all continents**,
- Inclusion of a **range of latitudes**,
- Coverage of **diverse Koppen climate zones**, where possible:
 - from 4 broad groups (A-D; no polar) at each continent
 - include important climate classes for each continent (e.g. 8 climate classes collectively occupy more than 97% of Australia's land)
note that selection will be limited to where the pollen is monitored and to sites that meet the criteria (next section).

SITE ELIGIBILITY REQUIREMENTS

Each selected site must meet **all** of the following criteria:

- **AIRBORNE POLLEN RECORDS**
 - **Continuous year-round pollen monitoring** (except during winter in snow-bound locations), with **main pollen season** included and with no significant disruptions; defined as sampling on **at least 75% of days in each sampling period** and ideally **at least 75% of days in each year**. When there is a gap between two sampling periods at the same site, and both records meet the criteria, both datasets will be considered.
 - If **more than 25% of days are missing**, a site may still be included if it represents a **climate class that is not well covered by nearby sites, and/or it occupies an unusual or underrepresented area**.
 - **Hirst-type or Rotorod** sampling monitors.
 - Available **daily concentrations for airborne Poaceae pollen and daily concentrations for total airborne (grass and all other) pollen**.
 - **No significant change in monitoring location (or method)**.
 - **At least 15 years** (for climate change part of the study priority will be given to sites with 30 years) of Poaceae pollen daily concentration records for **Northern Hemisphere**.
 - **At least 5 years** of Poaceae pollen daily concentration records for **Southern Hemisphere**.

- POACEAE OBSERVATION RECORDS
 - **At least 500 validated Poaceae observation records within 50 km** of a site (commonly used and representative for a site (Country) and preferably iNaturalist research-grade observations).
 - If a site does not have 500 iNaturalist research-grade observations, then:
 - Combine iNaturalist records with a secondary dataset to reach 500 records.
 - If combined iNaturalist and secondary dataset records are still below 500, then:
 - Include a third validated dataset to reach more than 500 records.
 - If none of the above thresholds are met, the site may still be included provided it has **at least 100 observation records, and represents a climate class that is not well covered by nearby sites and/or occupies an unusual or underrepresented area.**